

One-pot synthesis of 1,2,3-triazoles from α -oxonitriles^ψ

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Five 2-methyl-4-amino-5-aryl-1,2,3(2*H*)-triazoles have been synthesized from the reaction of α -oxonitriles with methylhydrazine in moderate yields.

In continuation of our earlier work¹ on the utilization of α -oxonitriles (**1**) in heterocyclic syntheses and as part of our research efforts to develop new potential antitumor agents, 4-amino-1,2,3(2*H*)-triazoles were synthesized from α -oxonitriles and methylhydrazine. 2-Substituted-4-amino-1,2,3(2*H*)-triazoles were prepared earlier² from other heterocycles involving cumbersome rearrangements.

α -Oxonitriles (**1**) reacted exothermally with methylhydrazine in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The reaction mixture on further heating afforded 2-methyl-4-amino-5-aryl-1,2,3(2*H*)-triazoles (**2**) in 42–52% yields and nearly always without the formation of any byproducts. In analogy with the reaction between α -oxonitriles and hydroxylamine^{1b}, the reaction between aryl cyanides (**1**) and methylhydrazine apparently involves the intermediate formation of α -amino- α' -arylglyoxal-bis-methylhydrazone (**2A**) which then loses a molecule of methylamine to give the heteroaromatic system **2**.

Ar = Ph, 3-CH₃.C₆H₄-, 4-CH₃/Cl/NO₂.C₆H₄-

The structure of **2** is based on their elemental analyses and spectral data (UV, IR, ¹H NMR and MS). The UV absorption of 2-methyl-4-amino-5-*m*-tolyl-1,2,3(2*H*)-triazole (**2b**) in methanol showed λ_{\max} at 232 nm which is quite typical for such triazoles². Its ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) spectrum showed an overlapping singlet of 6H intensity for the two methyl protons at δ 2.40 ppm, a multiplet of four aromatic protons at δ 7.13–8.05 and a signal of 2H intensity (D₂O exchangeable) for the amino protons at δ 11.86. Its IR

spectrum (nujol) revealed bands at 3400–3300 (NH₂), 1682 (C=N), 1620, 1589, 933 and 748 cm⁻¹. In the mass spectrum, the molecular ion peak of **2b** was observed at *m/z* 188 (M⁺).

Experimental

All m.ps. were determined in open capillaries with a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. The progress of the reaction and the purity of compounds were checked by TLC using silica gel G (E. Merck) plates. UV spectra were recorded on a Varian-Cary 2390 spectrophotometer, IR spectra on a Jasco FT-IR 5300 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra on a Jeol FX-90Q spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Hewlett-Packard LCMX 5989-In spectrometer.

α -Oxonitriles **1** were prepared by literature method³. Methylhydrazine was an Ega Chemie product.

All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

2-Methyl-4-amino-5-phenyl-1,2,3(2*H*)-triazole (2a) : To benzoyl cyanide (2.62 g, 20 mmol) was added dropwise methylhydrazine (2.1 g, 45 mmol) with stirring at room temperature. An exothermic reaction occurred with the evolution of methylamine. The reaction mixture was diluted with ethanol (30 ml) and refluxed on a steam-bath for 1 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the gummy mass obtained was dissolved in hot benzene and left in a desiccator for 2 days. The resulting white solid product was purified by preparative TLC using petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) as eluent and crystallized from benzene as white crystals (hygroscopic) (1.68 g, 48%) : m.p. 185–186°; ν_{\max} 3500–3400, 1688, 1630, 1580, 1560, 860, 800, 720 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 232 nm; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 10.72 (2H, s, NH₂, exch.), 8.66–7.12 (5H, m, ArH), 2.80 (3H, s, CH₃); *m/z* 174 (M⁺).

^ψPart-XII. For Part-XI, vide R. Lakhan and B. P. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect B*, 1999, 38, 979.

2-Methyl-4-amino-5-m-tolyl-1,2,3(2H)-triazole (2b) : To *m*-toluoyl cyanide (2.9 g, 20 mmol) was added methylhydrazine (2.1 g, 45 mmol) with stirring and the mixture refluxed for 4 h after dilution with absolute ethanol (30 ml). Following similar work-up the product was obtained as colourless crystals (1.6 g, 42%) : m.p. 350°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3400–3300, 1682, 1620, 1589, 933, 748 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 232 nm; δ (CDCl_3) 11.86 (2H, s, NH_2 , exch.), 8.05–7.13 (4H, m, ArH), 2.40 (6H, s, CH_3) *m/z* 188 (M^+).

2-Methyl-4-amino-5-p-tolyl-1,2,3(2H)-triazole (2c) : It was prepared from *p*-toluoyl cyanide as described above. Purification by preparative TLC followed by crystallization from benzene gave white crystals (1.65 g, 44%) : m.p. 180–181°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3480–3300, 1660, 1610, 1575, 962, 839, 756 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 232 nm; δ (CDCl_3) 10.30 (2H, br, NH_2 , exch.), 8.52–7.13 (4H, m, ArH), 2.46 (6H, s, CH_3); *m/z* 188 (M^+).

2-Methyl-4-amino-5-p-chlorophenyl-1,2,3(2H)-triazole (2d) : It was prepared from *p*-chlorobenzoyl cyanide as described above. Usual work-up and crystallization from benzene gave light violet crystals (2.1 g, 50%) : m.p. 220–221°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3450–3300, 1670, 1591, 933, 852, 808, 764 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 232 nm; δ ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) 12.33 (2H, br, NH_2 , exch.), 9.00–7.00 (4H, m, ArH), 2.60 (3H, s, CH_3).

2-Methyl-4-amino-5-p-nitrophenyl-1,2,3(2H)-triazole (2e) : It was prepared from *p*-nitrobenzoyl cyanide as described above. Usual work-up and crystallization from methanol gave brown crystals (2.3 g, 52%) : m.p. 170–171°; ν_{\max}

(nujol) 3460, 3364, 1670, 1620, 1601, 1580, 845, 771, 719 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 232 nm; δ ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) 9.44–6.00 (6H, m, 4 ArH and NH_2 , exch.), 2.66 (3H, s, CH_3).

Benzoylation of **2e** in pyridine at 5–10° gave a violet solid which was crystallized from benzene to give the *N*-benzoyl derivative of **2e** as light brown crystals (72%) : m.p. 100–101°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3500–3300 br (NH), 1790 (C=O), 1670 (C=N), 1601, 1583, 935, 808, 707 cm^{-1} .

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